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D2.8 First version of user requirements

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D2.8 First version of user requirements

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Executive summary

In line with the iterative and agile spiral model approach, the development of the VITALISE ICT tools incorporate user requirements and aim to provide convenient access to researchers. Said requirements are being collected between M6 and M24 and will provide insights and guidance to the developers of the ICT tools, under WP3, regarding the curation and access of the datasets, the desired UI and the functionality of the tools, all aimed to achieve increased acceptability by the researchers. In order to achieve this, a number of workshops and literature review, for each ICT tool, was conducted under Task 2.4 with perspective users of the tools. In addition, to further understand the researchers' needs, a questionnaire was developed, in an attempt to identify their attitude towards data sharing and further guide the developers of the ICT tools.

This document is the first version of the ICT tools user requirements and provides the rationale behind the development of the tools as well as a brief description of them, the methodology and tools used to conduct the workshops with researchers and collect their suggestions, opinions and concerns, and a brief description of the protocol used for the questionnaire. Also, this deliverable includes the refined outcomes of the workshops transformed into prioritized development requirements, as well as a summary of the questionnaire results and the requirements derived from them. Finally, the requirement prioritization and release planning are presented. The requirements presented in the document will be further refined during the Harmonization Board and Body meetings in order to assist the developers of the tools in their goal to create tools tailored to researchers' skills and needs.

The final version of the ICT tools requirements will be submitted at M24 of the VITALISE project in deliverable D2.9 "Final version of user Requirements."

1 Introduction

1.1 Purpose document

VITALISE designs and develops ICT tools for shared access of similar devices and applications used across Living Labs, as well as for collecting, storing and sharing datasets in order to facilitate access to data and technology for researchers in Living Lab research infrastructures. Moreover, VITALISE builds ICT tools and e-infrastructures that will be used by Living Lab researchers and will help harmonize and optimize their work. VITALISE designs and builds three main software tools: the panel management, the Accellup system and the RAI system and Discovery portal. The initial scope and description of the ICT tools was done during the preparation of the VITALISE Grant agreement, depicting the knowledge acquired regarding Living Labs and researchers' needs. This document analyzes and presents the first version of the user requirements for the three systems. The requirement elicitation procedures were based on co-design principles, involving the VITALISE consortium and external researchers in the process. Furthermore, the current version of the tools depicts also the long-term acquired experience of the three participating Living Lab networks, ENoLL, EIT Living Labs and Forum LLSA.

1.2 Document Structure

The deliverable is structured as such:

- **Section 1** (this section) provides information regarding the purpose of the document and makes an introduction on the drivers for the creations of the ICT tools.
- **Section 2** outlines the methodology followed for the collection of the first version of user requirements and the proposed methodological framework in line with the Harmonization procedure.
- **Section 3** discusses the results and presents the requirements for each tool.
- **Section 4** describes the envisaged releases and how they are aligned with other project activities.
- **Section 5** provides some concluded remarks for this deliverable.

1.3 The need for ICT tools for Living Labs

Panel management

“Panel management” as a term is used both in healthcare and business to refer to the coordination and research of a group of people that receive services from an organization. The group of people can refer to the population of patients that receive care from a healthcare facility or the group of consumers for a company.

Living Labs have adopted the term panel management to refer to a pre-existing group of pre-screened people (e.g., patients, practitioners etc.) who have given their consent to take part in different research activities over an agreed period. As the panel and systematic user involvement are some of the Living Labs building blocks (Veeckman et al., 2013), the panel management is of high importance for each living lab. The panel-based Living Lab approach implies a more permanent Living Lab infrastructure, as opposed to one-shot living lab applications, in which the most important and central "infrastructure" consists of a thematically recruited and profiled panel of users and yields many benefits for the Living Lab research and innovation processes (Schuurman & De Marez, 2012).

A well-planned panel management process allows the Living Lab to create meaningful activities and sustainable processes for the involvement of the different stakeholders. The process should include frequent communication (e.g., mailing bi-monthly newsletters, sharing results and pictures of the projects) and also ensures the careful planning and execution of the interactions among the wider network of all stakeholders who need to be involved, how, when, where and their role in the panel. For example, in a health-related Living Lab focused on older adults, their caregivers, families and

general practitioners should be included as well. Moreover, a survey on the motivations for collaboration showed that intrinsic motivations were highest among the panel members, meaning that panel members had a personal interest in making a valuable contribution to the innovation.

The use of an ICT tool for panel management means a strong decrease in time and effort required by panel managers, as all these processes can be tracked in a systematic way and planned properly.

Accellup system

One of the VITALISE goals is to promote scalability and exploitation of Health and Wellbeing Living Labs services at local, trans-regional and trans-national level in order to support research in the domain. Although the Living Lab research infrastructures are important for researchers in the Health and Wellbeing domain, Living Labs struggle to get offers for private projects beyond their network as it requires a lot of resources for a living lab to be visible beyond its network. Moreover, Living Labs do not know “how much to charge for their services”, the researchers and research groups do not know how much a Living Lab service costs and sometimes they are not aware of what a Living Lab can offer, up to what point and how they can get in touch with a Living Lab. These problems have been identified by ENoLL and the Health and Wellbeing Action Oriented Task Force during meetups and individual discussions with Living Lab members.

The proposed Accellup system aims to Increase visibility of Living Lab research infrastructures and their services, attracting researchers and private companies. In that way, the Living Labs will be able to create portfolio of completed jobs and get insights on what the price for their services are (demand and offer will stabilize the prices).

RAI system and Discovery portal

Open data sharing has gained great momentum with funding agencies as well as with publishers. The Transparency and Openness Promotion (TOP) Guidelines describe for all such stakeholders how to promote transparency, openness and reproducibility (Nosek, 2016). Already a few years after the publication of the guidelines, hundreds of publishers and journals — including Elsevier and Springer Nature — had signed up to the TOP guidelines (Gewin, 2016). This movement aims to counter the reproducibility crisis, as originally reported in fields like psychology (Aarts et al., 2015), but more recently also in the domains of digital medicine (Stupple et al., 2019) and artificial intelligence (Hutson, 2018)

Still, contemporary researchers find it difficult to get access to high quality data, or safe means to share such data. For example, in a Living Lab setting, data owners will not provide access without a non-disclosure agreement or reassurance given that trust and ethics are basic consideration in Living Labs methodological guidelines. While several existing communities for Medical Infrastructures are gaining popularity (e.g., the European Infrastructure for Translational Medicine (EATRIS) and the European Clinical Research Infrastructure Network (ECRIN)), their scope is limited to the (bio-)medical disciplines such as vaccine and drug development, or translational medicine. Within VITALISE, we aim to provide similar support to those scholars who seek or want to provide access to high quality data related to studies in ambulatory settings, in rehab centers, recreational spaces like gyms, and even citizens participating in studies where data is collected continuously. Sharing data from such studies is complicated, as acknowledged by a systematic review by van Panhuis et al. (Van Panhuis et al., 2014). That study lists 7 technical barriers, such as “Technical solutions not available”. The article clarifies that such solutions are critical to collect, harmonize (transformation and recoding to enhance inter-operability), integrate (combining harmonized datasets), and share complex and heterogeneous data. Within VITALISE, we aim to fill that gap specifically for data collected in a Living Lab setting. The Van Panhuis review lists various other barriers, including political and legal ones, such as “Lack of trust” and “Protection of privacy”. Within VITALISE such barriers were considered in the requirements analysis for the data sharing platform.

The building of this type of digital infrastructures has been recommended also by a 2018 European Commission Expert group on FAIR data (European Commission Expert Group on FAIR Data, 2018). Specifically, the second out of the seven recommendations were to develop better “FAIR ecosystems”. Basic ecosystem features include the issuing of digital object identifiers (DOIs) for data

sets are becoming mainstream. For example, the figshare.com website has facilitated over 30,000 citations of data to date. However, such websites do not yet provide features that address the trust and privacy barriers mentioned above.

2 Methodology for requirement elicitation

An important task for VITALISE is to identify early enough, basic user needs and requirements that will drive the implementation of the first prototypes. These prototypes will then be tested throughout the VITALISE agile requirement elicitation in line with the VITALISE Harmonization framework. The first step is to capture existing and validated knowledge during the first version of user requirement, primarily through consultation with the consortium and external researchers. This information is considered as the starting point, and it comes from discovering the existing needs of researchers and Living Labs. It is noted that, while defining user needs, the exploitation of VITALISE consortium expertise, built upon interaction with external researchers, was of high importance. Such an interaction has allowed technical partners to define key technical constraints that need to be considered. The two main sources of information for the first version of user requirements were the data collected through a questionnaire, as well as a number of specially organized workshops. Below we provide more information on the methodology followed and future steps.

2.1 Agile requirement elicitation in VITALISE

VITALISE Harmonization is taking place in two ends: Harmonization of processes and Harmonization of ICT tools used. It has already been designed and described a proposed Harmonization Framework that is presented in D2.1 Standard Version 1 and it will be further improved for the D2.2 Evaluation process and tools. The Harmonization Framework is a cyclic process that is planned to be repeated in a period of six months. In each iteration, the Harmonization Body will decide during the Co-creation phase which new ICT tools are needed or which existing/developed ones will be tested in the current iteration. After the Consensus and Approval phases (see D2.1 Standard Version 1 for more information) follows the Implementation phase in which the Living Labs of the consortium will deploy and use the tools that are delivered by the technical team. The goal is to promote the tools to external Living Labs through the VITALISE Harmonization Body, as they will participate in their evaluation and design. VITALISE envisions the adoption of the VITALISE ICT tools of the wider Living Lab and research community. When the real implementation finishes, the Living Labs and researchers will gather their suggestions for revisions and adjustments. These changes will be included in the D2.9 Final version of user requirements that will be an updated version of this document. The plan for technology releases that is in-line with the Harmonization Framework is presented in Section 4- Requirement prioritization and release planning of this document.

2.2 Questionnaire

VITALISE envisages Living Lab infrastructures as vehicles of facilitating and promoting research activities in Health Sciences and Wellness domains. To achieve this, VITALISE will Harmonize nine Living Labs across Europe and Canada, while at the same time it will develop and deploy ICT tools to further empower the ability of researchers to have access to research data, research infrastructure and verification tools. The Discovery Portal will be the ICT tool in the front-end through which the researchers will be able to access research data, perform analyses, verify their analyses and come into contact with peers. To achieve the maximum potential and impact, the Discovery portal will require availability of an extended library of datasets and as such, researchers will be required to make available their primary research data into the RAI system.

In order to optimize the ICT tools and specifically the Discovery Portal and make it attractive to researchers, a questionnaire on the attitudes of researchers towards data sharing has been developed (Appendix I). It aims to identify the key incentives that would promote data sharing in tandem with the concerns that such action arises. The questionnaire is comprised of questions, coming from previous similar published surveys, either edited to fit the scope of the project or unchanged (Berghmans et al., 2017; Kim & Stanton, 2016; von Bauer et al., 2015) with the addition of some novel ones. This quantitative approach will strengthen the qualitative approaches used for the elicitation of end-user needs. The questionnaire is divided into five categories, namely *demographics, data sharing experience, attitude towards data sharing, concerns and incentives* and includes 49 questions in total.

2.2.1 Methodology

The questionnaire was implemented in the EU survey tool, supported by the European Commission. The collection of responses ran between 20/12/2021 and 15/01/2022 and was anonymous. It received ethics approval by the Ethical Committee of the Aristotle University of Thessaloniki (No. 306356/2021). The dissemination of the questionnaire was performed via the social media channels of the project and in addition it was distributed to other cooperative projects in which the VITALISE consortium partners participate. The selected questions were either close ended with an option to provide free text if not satisfied by the available answer or utilised a seven level Likert scale. The collected answers were analysed using IBM SPSS 25.

The full questionnaire can be found here:

https://ec.europa.eu/eusurvey/runner/Data_Sharing_Opinions.

2.3 Workshops

Workshops are activities frequently used to collect the opinions of experts and stakeholders, concerning a specific subject (Gottesdiener, 2002). The open discussion taking place during the workshops, facilitated by a moderator, allows the natural interaction of participants, which greatly expedites the process of reaching an agreement regarding the various elements of the subject at a greater level of specificity.

The workshops, in consideration of the CoVID-19 pandemic restrictions, were carried out online, using virtual collaboration tools (Miro Boards) to make the experience more interactive. So far, three workshops, with an estimated duration of 60 minutes each, have been conducted. One workshop focused on the Panel Management, while the other two were on the RAI system (Certified Node & Cloud Server) and Discovery portal. More workshops may be carried out in the future, as the development of the systems evolves.

Each workshop consisted of four distinct sections, as presented in the table below.

Table 1 Workshop general structure

Section	Approximate Duration
1. Moderator's welcome, explanation of the purpose of the workshop	5 minutes
2. Introduction of the system/tool to be discussed (i.e., Panel management, RAI system, Discovery portal)	5 minutes
3. Open discussion facilitated by a moderator	45 minutes
4. Concluding remarks and thanks	5 minutes

3 First Version of User Requirements

3.1 Panel Management

The panel management is one of the identified services, provided by a Living Lab (<https://wiki.livinglab-harmonization.com/xwiki/bin/view/R%26D%20Services/4.4.20%20Panel%20management/>). As it is presented in D2.1 Standard Version 1, a panel is a pre-existing group of pre-screened people (e.g., patients, practitioners etc.) who have given their consent to take part in different research activities over an agreed period. Panel members have provided their contact details and other profiling information, which enables fast recruitment for specific research activities as they come up. Using the panel management software, it becomes easier for Living Labs to recruit, segment and maintain their panel or members. In addition to this, a panel management software allows panel managers to get insights quickly and easily from their panelists, create and manage a number of different panels, build rich profiles and also target segment of the panelist. A digital tool to manage all the contact information is mandatory, as it will reduce the management effort and provide valuable insights to the panel managers.

The panel management software provides features for storing, searching and identifying information that are used when a panel manager is communicating with the Living Lab panel. This information can include personal contact details for each member, previous interactions that have been done and details about the interaction. The manager can also schedule future interactions with the panel members. These interactions can be organized under events, that can be part of a larger project.

3.1.1 User Roles

The VITALISE panel management tool will support various Living Labs, hereafter referred to as “organization” for the scope of software requirements. In general, there are two types of users, the “Admin User” that is a super user and has access to all the information in the system, and the “Customer”, that refers to a specific organization. Each organization will handle its own panel information. Taking that into account, we have identified the following user roles for the customer user type (Figure 1), for the panel management tool.

- **Owner:** is the owner of an organization, the person responsible for the specific organization and all the procedures that the organization performs in the panel management tool
- **Manager:** the manager is assigned by the owner and is a user that can invite people to an organization or assign new managers.
- **Invited:** a user that is invited by a manager to the organization
- **Applicant:** a user that wants to register themselves in an organization
- **Member:** a user that is an approved member of an organization. The member is a stakeholder of the organization that participates in projects, events and studies.
- **Seceder:** a user that left from organization
- **Exile:** a user that is banned from organization by manager

Figure 1 Panel management user types and the links among them

3.1.2 Actions Per Role

Through the performed workshops and the experience of Living Lab networks and AUTH, which is the main responsible for panel management, the following building blocks of the VITALISE panel management have been identified:

Member Profile

- Contains all the information for a specific user, including: name, address, contact details, photo
- Contains information about the projects and events a member is participating in

Projects

- A project includes several activities, referred to as events
- The project should have an identity that is added from the beginning, including: name, start-end date, logo, ethical approval, consent template
- In project view, all the participants that have been tagged in the project should appear

Events

- One event can have several project tags (one event can be part of several projects) or untagged
- The event should have an identity that is added from the beginning, including: name, start-end date, project, place (map or zoom link)
- In event view, all the participants that have been tagged in the event should be seen

Based on those building blocks, we have identified specific actions per user role that are presented below and summarized also in Figure 2.

Owners

The owner can perform all the actions that a manager can do with the addition that the owner is the only user that can remove managers and update their profiles.

Manager

- As a manager, I want to search and see all the users that belong to my organisation
- As a manager, I want to view and update my own profile
- As a manager, I want to update the profiles of the members in my organization
- As a manager, I want to ban/unban members from my organization to avoid misuse behaviour

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- As a manager, I want to completely remove members from my organization (make them exiles)
- As a manager, I want to invite managers/members to my organization

Member

- As a member, I want to search and see the managers and owner that belong to my organisation
- As a member, I want to view and update my own profile
- As a member, I want to be able to leave from an organization (become seceder)

Figure 2 Panel management user actions per role

Managers would also like to have the following functionalities:

- As a manager, I would like to search all members in a project and open the personal contact details
- As a manager, I would like to search all members in an event and open the personal contact details
- As a manager, I would like to see the pending confirmations (about events' invitations)
- As a manager, I would like to search for members based on criteria:
 - Age group
 - Gender
 - Type of stakeholder (member tags e.g., older adults, doctor)
 - Available Means of communication (e.g., only people that are using viber)
 - Project
 - Event
 - Home address

3.1.3 Risks and motivators

Some of the challenges and motivators identified during the workshop are summarized here:

- The role of the panel manager should be distinctive in the organization. The panel manager is responsible for monitoring the panel management tool.
- Security issues were discussed as the tool will store information about panel members that should be protected.
- An important motivator is to create a tool that is easily integrated with all the other tools used by Living Lab researchers and managers in order to avoid losing time in changes among platforms.
- The member's user profile should go beyond simple demographic information and should include more details about the user (e.g. distinguish ambassadors, lead users, segmentation of panel, preferences in communication means)
- The tool should not be project-based as it increases the time needed to communicate with new people when a project ends.

3.2 Accellup

In an attempt to find the most appropriate and sustainable business model for Living Labs, VITALISE

creates a new software, the Accellup system. The idea is inspired by existing freelancing platforms (e.g., freelancer.com) and booking platforms (booking.com). In freelancer.com anyone can create and account as a recruiter or as a person looking for work. When you first register in the site, it requires to fix your profile based on what you would like to do (Figure 3) In each account you can have both the jobs you applied for and the jobs you are looking for employees. You also have a profile in which you can add information for yourself and your skills but also the system calculates some automatic Key Performance Indicators (KPIs) from your performance. A similar platform is also the UpWork.com.

Another widely used platform that was investigated for preparing the Accellup system requirements, is the booking.com. In booking you can post your accommodation facilities and make them available for people to rent. Users of the Booking.com can search based on various criteria (e.g. dates, facilities, price) and select

Figure 3 Freelancer first registration

the one that fits their needs.

Just like anyone can post a job in freelancing platforms, any company, research group or individual research will be able to post a description of an activity in Accellup system. Similar to Booking.com, they can also search for Living Labs and the previous works that they have done based on information that they put and the KPIs that are manually calculated. The Living Labs of the network can assess the work that is required and make a bid. Then the customer can choose the bid that best fits its needs based on a variety of criteria. This will be handled through a web platform, the Accellup system, that will ensure the safe payment, completion of tasks and quality of services.

3.2.1 User Roles

The main user roles that are identified for the Accellup system are summarized below: As the terms that will be used in the final system have not been agreed yet, we present multiple terms for each role.

- **Super user/Admin:** this is the user that is responsible for the entire system and its smooth operation.
- **Assigners/project creators:** Organizations (SMEs, academia, industry etc.) looking for someone to complete/assign a work/project
- **Freelancers/assignees/ Living Labs:** Organizations (basically Living Labs) that are undertaking the work/project

- **Investors:** investors can see projects that have bids but do not have budget from the assigners and can provide the money for the implementation. This role is not included in the current implementation but is envisaged to be implemented in future prototypes of the system

3.2.2 Actions Per Role

Through discussions with experts in the field and considering the functionalities offered by similar tools, we have identified the following requirements for each role.

Super user

- As a super user, I want to be able to add or remove expertise fields.
- As a super user, I want to be able to add or remove offered services.
- As a super user, I want to be able to ban any user that does not comply with the community rules.
- As a super user, I want to receive complaints for a user in a simple complain form (e.g., if payment not made, if work is not done well)
- As a super user I want to receive notification for new requested authorization of freelancers, with all the information available in the profile.
- As a super user, I want to approve or disapprove the authorization requests of freelancers by clicking a button.
- Super User will have access to all information in the system, regardless of if they are sealed or private for an account.

Assigners/ project creators

- As an assigner, I want to be able to change basic information on my profile or delete them.
- As an assigner I want to see information my projects (open, terminated or accepted)
- As an assigner, I want to define a project that I want to be undertaken including things like:
 - Name
 - General description
 - Expected outcomes
 - Required services (from a list)
 - Estimated budget (min / max) – hourly budget (optional)
 - Region/location of interest (optional)
 - Attach file (images or documents) (optional)
- As an assigner, I want to be able to choose if my project will be publicly available or available only to authorized freelancers.
- As an assigner, I want to select if the bids for my project will be publicly available or sealed. Sealed bids can be seen only by me and the Super User.
- As an assigner I want to limit the number of offers I will accept.
- As an assigner I want to set expiration for accepting bids.
- As an assigner, I want to receive all bids that are made for my project in a list.
- As an assigner I want to be able to change my project details.
- As an assigner, I want to see other projects that have been posted from other assigners.
- If I change something to my project, a notification is sent to all freelancers that have done a bid.
- As an assigner I want to accept a bid at any time. If a bid is accepted the project is closed.
- If no offer fits my needs, I want to be able close/terminate the project.
- If I terminate the project without approval of any bid, I want to be able to provide a reason for the termination in free text.
- As an assigner I can receive messages from freelancers that have made a bid for my project
- As an assigner I can ask for more information from freelancers that have placed a bid via the message option

- As an assigner, I want to be able to post a comment for the freelancers that have completed a work and a simple rate (e.g., 1-5 stars)
- As an assigner I can post a project and tagged it as “Looking for investors”, instead of offering a budget range

Freelancers/assignees actions

- As a freelancer, I want to be able to update basic information on my profile or delete them.
- As a freelancer I want to see in one page the available projects that are related to my expertise and provided services.
- As a freelancer, I want to see the projects that I have undertaken (past projects)
- As a freelancer I want to see my bids (open, closed and approved)
- As a freelancer, I want to be able to place a bid for a project by adding information like estimated cost, estimated days, expertise of people involved and general description (optional)
- As a freelancer I want to see other available bids for the projects that do not have sealed bids
- As a freelancer, I want to be able to filter the projects posted based on categories and/or key words.
- As a freelancer, I want to be able to change my bid at any time while the project is open for bids.
- As a freelancer, I want to contact assigners by sending a message to request further information about a project. A message can be sent only when a bid is made.
- As a freelancer I want to receive a notification when a project that I have placed a bid for, have some information changes.
- As a freelancer, I want to be able to withdraw my bid at any time until it is selected by the assigner.
- As a freelancer, I want to be able to post a comment and rate for the assigners that I completed I work for
- After selection the freelancer should accept -> create a contract
- As a freelancer, I want to be able to communicate with the Admin for any complaints that I might have (simple complaint form)
- As a freelancer I want to see both projects looking for bids but also projects that are looking for investors
- As a freelancer, I want to be able to bid for projects that are tagged as “looking for investors”

Investors

- As an investor, I want to see the projects that are tagged as “looking for investors” and already have bids from freelancers. Projects that are tagged as “looking for investors” but do not have bids, will not be available for investment.
- As an investor, I want to select the preferable bid for the project that I am going to invest in.

3.2.3 Risks and motivators

Some of the key points that are requested by Living Labs to be considered when designing the system are:

- A Living Lab might not be able to undertake a whole project by his own and might not be able to address the issue. We should be able to combine more than one Living Lab for a specific demand
- We must try to raise everyone up and not create services for maintaining some at the top
- We should try to involve more mature and experienced Living Labs with less mature ones and try to learn from each other
- It is difficult for a Living Lab to operate in other countries, especially in the healthcare sector were “standards” change among countries. Living Labs can help external companies to explore the local culture.

- We should be careful not to drop prices too much as some Living Lab might have lower prices than others
- This can be a platform where companies can find info about the Living Lab
- We should invest on the element of community and balance, offer what each Living Lab would like to do and what they know

3.3 RAI system and Discovery portal

VITALISE proposes to open access to Living Labs' captured data for processing, enabling open, fair and reliable Research Community where every researcher will be accredited for their work and all research data will be equally accessible for processing without violating data protection regulations. In this sense, VITALISE introduces the Research Analysis Identifier (RAI) and the VITALISE e-infrastructure that will support research and data analysis services.

The RAI identifier is aimed at becoming an immutable identifier for a reliable research experiment results referencing, which include information on the experiment dataset, processing script, authorship, timing and produced results, encrypted and stored within a blockchain network. In few words it's aimed to become, the DOI of the scientific results analysis.

The VITALISE e-infrastructure's main components are the RAI Certified Nodes, the Discovery portal (depicted as RAI Finder Service in the figure below), and the RAI Cloud Server (depicted as RAI Registration Service in the figure below).

The RAI Certified Nodes are going to be installed in each living lab and are responsible for (1) collecting, preparing and transforming data (for each living lab) into harmonised VITALISE data model, (2) informing and updating Discovery portal on data available for research, (3) generating synthetic data (representing real data) to allow researchers to developed algorithm locally on their PCs, (4) executing external researchers developed algorithms with the real data, (5) requesting scientific results registration upon external researchers request.

The discovery portal is the common entry point for external researchers to (1) query and identify Living Lab available research data, (2) interact with the RAI Certified Node containing the data of interest, for getting a synthetic version of the data, for remotely testing locally developed algorithms with real data and registering results, and (3) to resolve and identify research assets and information for a given RAI identifier. Additionally, the discovery portal is the common entry point for the different VITALISE ICT tools.

The RAI Cloud Server is responsible for guaranteeing the perdurance of research analysis results in time and registering the information and research assets involved in a scientific experiment, upon a researchers request. These assets and information will be encrypted and written into blockchain network, producing a RAI identifier.

Figure 4 RAI system overview

3.3.1 Workshop results

3.3.1.1 User Roles

As previously mentioned, the VITALISE e-infrastructure's main components are the RAI Certified Nodes, the Discovery portal, and the RAI Cloud Server. The RAI Certified nodes will be installed in each living lab and only specific personnel may interact with them. The Discovery portal is the main application that will allow researchers to interact with the rest of the system. The RAI Cloud Server operates in the background, thus there are no direct interactions with the users.

Given these three components of the system, during the two workshops four distinct roles were identified:

1. Controller: The “owner” of the datasets uploaded from a Living Lab and the manager of the RAI Certified Node installed in a Living Lab. Users that may undertake the responsibilities of this role are:
 - a. Living Lab/Data manager,
 - b. Project/Pilot manager,
 - c. Panel manager,
 - d. Business developer of the living lab,
 - e. Information Specialist/Librarian.
2. Processor: Individuals (or organizations) that wish to gain access to and process the uploaded datasets through the Discovery portal. User types under the umbrella of this role are:
 - a. External researcher, i.e., researchers that do not belong to an organization or institute that has direct access to a RAI Certified Node that wish to perform an analysis, as well as researchers that belong to an organization or institute that has direct access to a RAI Certified Node but wish to perform analysis on datasets belonging to another RAI Certified node.
 - b. Teachers that may use datasets or the system for educational purposes.
3. Administrator: The technical partner(s) responsible for the operation and maintenance of the system,
4. Public: Individuals that have no active role in the processing of datasets. Users pertaining to this role may be:

- a. Journal editors,
- b. Members of the public.

3.3.1.2 Actions Per Role

Given the specificity of the three components, as presented above, all actions have been categorized into three distinct categories and subsequently allocated to sub-categories. The categories are:

1. Datasets, distinguished into four sub-categories (Upload, Search/View, Synthetic data, and Other).
2. Analysis, further separated into five sub-categories (Upload script, Run script, Get results. Resolve RAI Identifier, Other).
3. Forum, divided into three sub-categories (Submit request, Identify potential partners, Submit complaint).

Controllers will usually perform their actions through the RAI Certified Nodes and through indirect interactions with the RAI Cloud Server. Processors may execute their actions only through the Discovery Portal, interacting with the rest of the system through background operation. The administrator may interact with all components of the system, while public users may perform their limited actions through the Discovery Portal.

Controller

Table 2 Controller actions

Category		As a controller, I want to be able to...
Datasets	Upload	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Upload datasets. 2. Set the availability/visibility of all datasets I have uploaded. 3. Provide access to other researchers to upload their own datasets (become a controller). 4. Manage the metadata of the datasets I have uploaded. 5. Include the protocol of the study in the metadata of the datasets I have uploaded. 6. Describe the level of privacy of the data included in the uploaded dataset (if they are fully anonymized or not).
	Search/View	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 7. View all datasets in the network i.e., look for dataset statistics, topics, specifically which are missing, which are mostly used, as well as which instruments/sensors are mostly used. 8. View/Access statistics on dataset visibility, dataset usage, and produced from the RAI server/node.
	Synthetic data	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 9. Show the privacy metrics and confirm the metrics that are over the threshold of the synthetic data I have generated.
	Other	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 10. Install the RAI node in a local computer through easy steps. 11. Mark a data structure and format that has been officially accepted in the harmonization process.
Analysis	Upload script	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 12. View and/or check the scripts uploaded by researchers for the analysis of datasets I have uploaded. 13. Initiate the automated flagging for malicious scripts.
	Run script	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 14. Approve the scripts and analysis of researchers on datasets I have uploaded. 15. Launch the analysis a researcher has requested to perform on datasets I have uploaded.

	Get results	16. Access/View statistics about the analysis done in datasets I have uploaded.
	Resolve RAI Identifier	17. Verify RAI identifiers.
	Other	18. Ensure that the results of the analysis maintain data security, before allowing the resolution of the RAI Identifier.
Forum	Submit request	19. Receive notification and access/view categorized requests for datasets.
	Identify potential partners	<i>No action considered for this role as of yet.</i>
	Submit complaint	20. Receive notifications and access/view complaints regarding data models, their extensions and possible changes that can be applied to them.

Processor (Researcher)

Table 3 Processor actions

Category		As a processor, I want to be able to...
Datasets	Upload	1. Become a controller, i.e., upload my own datasets on a RAI Certified node.
	Search/View	2. Search available datasets and view <ol style="list-style-type: none"> background information on data collection procedures of the dataset, what studies have been published based on the datasets, other results of the analysis performed on a dataset, as well as requests for the synthetic data of the dataset, usage statistics of the datasets, descriptive statistics of the datasets, licensing or possible restrictions when using the datasets. 3. Search for available datasets based on topics, country of origin, organization, users etc.
	Synthetic data	4. Request synthetic data for a specific dataset. 5. Receive synthetic data for a specific dataset. 6. View metrics related to the quality of the synthetic data. 7. Choose the synthetic data format type (csv, json, etc.).
	Other	8. Have access to both quantitative and qualitative data. 9. Rate a dataset. 10. See user rating of a dataset. 11. Share a link to a dataset.
Analysis	Upload script	12. Choose a dataset of interest and upload a script file to perform my preferred analysis.
	Run script	13. Develop and run locally script on synthetic data before initiating the actual analysis. 14. Have the option to run a script on multiple datasets from the same RAI node.

		15. Receive feedback on the running time of my analysis.
	Get results	16. View the results of my analysis. 17. Download my results in a format of my choosing (spv, csv, json, etc.).
	Resolve RAI Identifier	18. Resolve RAI identifiers for the authentication of my analysis.
	Other	19. Share a link to the results of my analysis. 20. View publications based on my analysis.
Forum	Submit request	21. Access the forum and submit a request for a specific dataset. 22. Request clarifications on a dataset's variables, metadata, etc..
	Identify potential partners	23. View affiliations of the controller and other processors at a person/organization level.
	Submit complaint	24. Access the forum and submit a complaint about a specific dataset or other issues.

Administrator

Table 4 Administrator actions

Category		As an administrator, I want to be able to...
Datasets	Upload	1. Add and remove users.
	Search/View	2. Govern the approval process for a processor to gain access to a dataset.
	Synthetic data	<i>No action considered for this role as of yet.</i>
	Other	3. Grant access rights to controllers.
Analysis	<i>Not applicable.</i>	
Forum	Submit request	<i>No action considered for this role as of yet.</i>
	Identify potential partners	<i>No action considered for this role as of yet.</i>
	Submit complaint	4. Evaluate complaints. 5. Update data models based on complaints.

Public User

Table 5 Public user actions

Category		As a public user, I want to be able to...
Datasets	Upload	<i>Not applicable.</i>
	Search/View	
	Synthetic data	
	Other	1. View publications that have used one or more datasets.
Analysis	Upload script	<i>Not applicable.</i>
	Run script	
	Get results	
	Resolve RAI Identifier	2. Verify the analysis and its results.
	Other	<i>No action considered for this role as of yet.</i>
Forum	<i>Not applicable.</i>	

3.3.1.3 Risks and motivators

Some risks and motivators, specific to the roles of controller and processor, were identified during the workshop and are outlined below.

Controller

Risks:

- The role of the controller encapsulates many responsibilities, which may prove to be very time-consuming. Thus, the system should have a user-friendly front end to make the process easier and faster.
- Given that the controller's approval is necessary in some stages of the analysis, the individual(s) in this role should take notice as to not serve as a bottleneck.
- The possibility of data breach in case of inadequate anonymization should be minimized.
- The controllers should have the capability to add information to their datasets overtime, especially in the case of longitudinal data, as well as retract data and whole datasets.
- The future sustainability of the infrastructure was discussed as it constitutes a key factor related to long term dataset management.
- Privacy issues were discussed during the workshop as they affect the willingness and/or capability of the controller to upload datasets.

Motivators:

- An important motivator for the controllers would be the possibility to gain "data publication" points via a national system as a reward for uploading their datasets.
- The RAI System may serve as a private cloud back up, thus protecting the controller from critical data loss.

Processor (Researcher)

Risks:

- The processor should be able to somehow ascertain the quality of the datasets they are planning to analyze. A 5-star system for each dataset can be adapted.
- The information and variable naming schema attached to a dataset should be configured in an informative manner.
- The processor should be assured of the compliance of datasets to GDPR and ethics regulations.
- There is always the risk that the uploaded data may not be enough to achieve critical mass but VITALISE serves as a starting point in addressing this issue globally.

Motivators:

- A significant motivator for processors is that they would have the ability to do research without having to collect data on their own.
- The processor's contribution to open science and to making the replication of research much easier is an important motivator.

3.3.2 Questionnaire on attitudes of researcher towards data sharing

3.3.2.1 Demographics

In total 75 filled questionnaires were filled by researchers in the field of health sciences and wellness the most of which (68%) had less than 15 years of experience in research. They also reported that they primarily work in academia (68%) and that they are responsible for both writing research proposals and the execution of research projects (61.3%). More than half of the respondents (50.7%) reported that their primary funding source is a regional research funder e.g., European Commission followed by a state or subject-specific research funder (40%).

Regarding data storage and sharing, 72% reported that they store their research data locally and not in a cloud service, while 17.3% have experienced data loss. Back-ups in a separate location from the primary storage has not been kept by 10.7% of the respondents, and from those that keep back-ups, close to half (47.8%) do it in regular intervals. A last question was only addressed to those that responded that they keep back-ups and 40.3% responded that only themselves can recover data from their back-up.

3.3.2.2 Data sharing experience

The questionnaire had seven questions related to the data sharing experience of the respondents, three referred to the last time they shared data a four to the last two years. Regarding the way the last time they shared data, the data recipients gained access, 40% responded via cloud storage (Dropbox, Google Docs, OneDrive etc.), 6.7% replied that they have never shared data, while the second most popular answer was physical disks/email. On the question about the interoperability of data, the most popular choice (57.3%) was that the lastly shared data were in a standard file format (e.g., CSV, JSON). The third question was about the structured of the data lastly shared, where nearly half the respondents (48%) replied that they used a clear schema (self-defined columns that were documented clearly). Interestingly, 10 (13.3%) replied "Not applicable/Do not understand" in the last question.

Figure 5. Last two years data sharing experience answers

When asked about the last two years, the participants were asked if they have uploaded data in a DOI-oriented data repository, have uploaded data into a public web-space, provided access to their data by publishing supplement materials for articles or were asked to share their data. In the first three questions, half of the respondents replied that they didn't upload or shared any data in the last two years. The last question 62.6% of the respondents had been asked to share data at least once during the last two years.

3.3.2.3 Attitude

The attitude section of the questionnaire was comprised of three parts. The first one was about the perceived data sharing culture in each respondent's discipline, followed by questions regarding their own beliefs towards data sharing. The last part was about factors taken into account when considering the usage of research data belonging to others.

In the first section the questions with interesting responses were about articles being more likely to be accepted for publication (46.6% answered slightly agree and above) if author provides open access to data and that 52% answered at least slightly agree that researchers, in their discipline, rely on research data shared with them.

In the part regarding the participants' own beliefs, strong majority (84.1%) agreed that archiving their research data will help them or team members to reproduce results in the future, while 54.7% agreed that sharing data is their moral obligation because of their funding source. Interestingly, 13.3% of the respondents strongly disagree with the previous sentence. Lastly, 74.7% agreed that sharing data is a scientific obligation since it allows verification, replication and building further research.

The last part the participants considered good documentation (82.7%), citations in formal literature (52%), a good personal (45.3%) or institutional (48%) reputation the most important factors when deciding to use other's research data.

3.3.2.4 Concerns

A total of ten questions was dedicated to the researchers' concerns towards data sharing. The questions referred to issues often faced by researchers in their projects' course. These issues range from legal restrictions (GDPR, copywrites, patents etc.) to resources required, fear of making mistakes and misinterpretations and misuse. The most prominent concerns that researchers reported keep them from sharing data were GDPR related restrictions (80% agreement), non-GDPR related restrictions (65.3% agreement) and increased effort of time and cost (66.7% agreement).

Clear majorities were observed regarding the lack of motivation (53.3% agreement), the risk of misinterpretation of data (57.4% agreement) and potential undesired commercial uses (52%). The respondents didn't provide a clear picture when asked if the danger of misuse or the fear of making a mistake kept them from sharing data. Noteworthy is the fact that, with the exception of GDPR related restrictions, the neutral option had a mean value of 17.03%.

3.3.2.5 Incentives

The final section of the questionnaire was devoted in identifying possible incentives that would motivate researchers to share research data. The section included eight questions with potential incentives ranging from moral incentives such as recognition and self-esteem, financial incentives such as expense allowances and discounts in journals, and career related incentives such as the provision of support and the consideration of research data as relevant scientific output. Almost all incentives received predominantly positive responses. In descending order, 88% of the respondents agreed that increased visibility and impact would motivate them to share research data, followed by the making of new contacts (87.9%), the consideration of research data as scientific output (84.5%) and recognition in the scientific community (78.7%). Under 75% of agreement was reported for the provision of support in the process of making data accessible (74.7%), the establishment of standards for accountability and appropriate use of the data (73.4%), followed by the financial incentives which received agreement by the 70.7% of the participants. Increased self-esteem as an incentive to share research data was the question least agreed upon with 46.7% of the respondents agreeing.

Figure 6. Distribution of answers in questions regarding possible motivators

3.3.2.6 Data Sharing Requirements

This section of the deliverable presents the key needs, concerns and incentives, for sharing data, identified by the questionnaire respondents. The selection criteria were a difference of 40% between agreements and disagreements as well as the relevance to the envisaged functionality of the Discovery Panel tool. Additionally, to the presentation of the key findings, Table 6 also includes the way VITALISE addresses each one.

Table 6. List of data sharing requirements

Requirement		VITALISE address
Needs	DOI-oriented depository	The RAI System will provide solutions to the identified needs by facilitating a safe and easy to use repository in addition to being able to easy verify the dataset and the performed analysis using RAI identifiers.
	Supplementary material of articles	
	Easy and safe way of data sharing	
Concerns	GDPR restrictions	VITALISE will harmonize the ethical procedures including, but not limited to, GDPR related restrictions. The Discovery Panel will provide easy to use guides to achieve compliance to the legal and ethical requirements of research.
	Non-GDPR restrictions	
	Increased effort	The RAI system will provide an easy-to-use method of verifying datasets and analyses.
	Risk of misinterpretation or falsification of data	RAI system saves experiment components (including results) or their hashes to the blockchain, so they will be immutable and clearly identifying the source datasets
Incentives	Visibility, recognition, and new contacts	The Discovery panel will have a forum functionality.
	Research data to be considered as relevant scientific output	The wide adoption of RAI identifier by journals can help towards the establishing research data as relevant scientific output.
	Establishment of standards	VITALISE harmonizes the models used for data across Living Lab, based on existing, widely adopted standards.
	Support in the process of making data accessible	The Discovery panel will have detailed guides on how to upload data.
	Financial Incentives	Possible journal discounts along with RAI identifier. To be considered in the business exploitation plan

4 Requirement prioritization and release planning

The methodology for capturing requirements for the different ICT tools, has allowed to identify potential needs and wishes from a diverse user base. Additionally, technical team from WP3 has identified different technology approaches to respond to requirements coming from GA and those being captured following the established user requirements capturing methodology.

As time and available effort within VITALISE project are limited, an agile iterative approach has been adopted to increasingly build functionalities into prototypes, to contrast each prototype with users representing different stakeholder roles and to prioritize next iterations functionalities and to implement refinements and bug fixing required. Each iterative prototype cycle is planned to end-up in a prototype delivery. Initial release plan is as follows:

Phase	Targeted month	Related project events	Harmonization Framework events
Prototype v1.0 – initial concept implementation for testing from central demonstration deployment	M12	MS3: First Release of H&W Living Lab Research Infrastructure Tools (M12) Early version for internal testing purposes (within the consortium)	Release of Standard Version 2
Prototype v2.0 – initial implementation for Vitalise LL deployment and initial in-house testing	M16	D3.4: Panel Management Tool (M16) – End of task T3.7. D3.6: Certified Node OS installation image (M16) T3.1 reference to “open the VITALISE virtual access in stages, with a first opening at M18 ”	In time for the implementation phase for the Standard Version 3. Release of Standard Version 3, with integration of the feedback gathered from Prototype v2.0.
Prototype v3.0 – revised implementation for Vitalise LL deployment and	M22	End of most relevant WP3 technical development tasks at M22	In time for the implementation phase for the Standard Version 4
Final ICT tools version	M32	End of WP3 activities at M22 MS4: Final Release of H&W Living Lab Research Infrastructure Tools (M36)	Final piloting in Virtual Access (WP12)

5 Conclusion

This Deliverable presents the first version of VITALISE ICT tools user requirements for the three tools envisaged to be built during VITALISE project, namely: the panel management, the Accellup system and the RAI system and Discovery portal. The requirements were based on the initial presentation of the tools and feedback gathered through workshops and a questionnaire to health science and wellbeing researchers. The user roles for each tool are presented and then we describe what each role is envisaged to do in the system.

The questionnaire employed a quantitative approach to identify the attitudes of researchers towards data sharing. It included questions regarding their experiences, concerns and possible motivators. The most prominent findings were that researchers feel that they are hindered by legislation and the increased effort related to data sharing, as well as that they would be motivated to share data if that data was considered a scientific outcome and would provide them with increased visibility. The current version of the requirements will drive the creation of prototype v1.0 that will then be updated based on the feedback gathered through the iterative and agile approach of the VITALISE development.

Based on the initial workshops, Panel management and Accellup system seem to be required by the Living Lab community and can help them optimize their management and gain visibility. However, there are existing threats that were presented, basically regarding security of the systems and how we ensure equality in access. VITALISE will investigate them further within the agile development process. Furthermore, the requirements summarize the basic actions that a user will do in the two systems, from one hand handle the interactions with the panel of stakeholders with the use of panel management and on the other hand, having access to new income opportunities with Accellup system. Future steps are to gather feedback from the real use of system increments and start defining the system views and focus on usability and ease of use. More specific testing and validation will be organized for new features added based within the consortium and beyond. The tools will be also tested during the visits of the external researchers.

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Appendices

Appendix 1 – Questionnaire on attitudes of researchers on data sharing

Questionnaire on attitudes of researchers towards data sharing

Researchers in the Health and Wellbeing domain need 1) convenient access to research infrastructures, 2) direct engagement of people in order to validate hypotheses, co-design solutions and services, evaluate their feasibility and effectiveness and participate in the translation and mobilization of outcomes and 3) experience from multidisciplinary domains (e.g., healthcare management, assistive technologies, data science) to deal with the complexity of health and wellbeing research.

Over the last few years, Living Labs have emerged as resilient research and innovation infrastructures and have proved to be key to the integration of research and innovation processes in real life settings, focusing primarily on people and their engagement in research procedures. VITALISE opens up Living Lab Infrastructures as a means to facilitate and promote research activities in the Health and Wellbeing domain in Europe and beyond by enabling in person Transnational Access to 17 Living Lab research infrastructures and by supporting remote digital access to datasets (Virtual Access) of rehabilitation, transitional care and everyday life activities through harmonized processes and common tools. VITALISE will design and develop ICT tools for shared access of similar devices and applications used across Living Labs, as well as for collecting, storing and sharing datasets. Lastly, VITALISE will invest in the development of Training methods towards the wider understanding and valorisation of Living Lab methodologies in the research community.

This questionnaire is to be filled by researchers in the field of health sciences and wellness. If your work is not in these fields we would like to thank you for your interest and ask you to please close this tab.

We are collecting data, via this questionnaire, to assess your attitudes towards research data sharing. Your answers will be used during the design phase of the ICT tools for the collection, storing and sharing of research datasets.

Should you accept to participate in this study, you will be asked to fill out this anonymous questionnaire which can be divided in five sectors: 1) demographics, 2) data sharing experiences, 3) attitude towards data sharing, 4) concerns that prevent you from sharing data and 5) incentives that would motivate you to share data.

Your participation is voluntary. You can withdraw from this study, without any data being saved, at any time by closing this tab. The collected information will be anonymous, confidential, will be only used for the aforementioned study and will not be transferred to third countries.

Every processing of personal data is made in accordance with the General Data Protection Regulation (GDPR) along with the implementation of the appropriate technical and organizational measures. Your personal data is kept only for the period required for the specific lawful purposes for which it was collected. Furthermore, the safe destruction of personal data is ensured by the time the legally prescribed period has elapsed or the purpose of the processing ceases to exist and there is no legal requirement or legal interest or legal right to continue keeping them. You can find out more about the Privacy Policy of Auth at <https://www.auth.gr/en/gdpr-en>. As soon as your answers are submitted, the verification of your identity is no longer required by those responsible for processing your personal data (controllers) for the purposes

D2.8 First version of user requirements

of the research. Consequently, the controllers are not obliged to obtain or maintain or process additional information for the purpose of verification your identity. Accordingly, the following rights do not exist: a) the right of access to your personal data, b) the right to rectification, c) the right to erasure, d) the right to restriction of processing and e) the right to data portability in accordance with the GDPR.

Even though we aren't collecting personal data, if you have any questions for your personal data or your rights and you believe that they are violated, you can contact Aristotle's University DPO at data.protection@auth.gr and we will answer as soon as possible, or you can submit a complaint with the Hellenic Data Protection Authority at dpa.gr.

Principal Investigator: Prof. Panagiotis Bamidis, bamidis@auth.gr

A1. How many years have you been engaged in research activities?

- Under 5
- 6-10
- 11-15
- 16-20
- 20+

A2. Concerning research projects, you are mostly responsible for:

- Execution of research projects
- Writing of research proposals
- Equally responsible for both
- Other

A3. Which of the following best describes your primary work sector?

- Academic
- Public
- Private
- Non-profit
- Other

A4. What is your primary funding source for all your projects in the last five years?

- A country - or subject-specific research funder e.g. a research council
- A corporate/private/commercial organization
- Self-funded
- A regional research funder: e.g. European Commission
- My institution
- A charity or other 'third sector' funder
- Crowd-funded
- Don't know
- Other

A5. Where do you usually store you research data?

- Locally
- Cloud service

A6. Have you ever experienced research data loss?

- Yes
- No
- Other/Comment

A7. Do you keep back-ups on a location separate from where the data is stored?

- Yes, structured daily/weekly/monthly snapshots
- Yes, but only anecdotally
- No

A1. The last time you shared research data, how did the recipients gain access?

- Via DOI-oriented data archive/repository (Figshare, Zenodo etc.)
- As supplementary material on publisher website
- Via personal or institutional website

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- Via institutional server/drive (FTP, SMB etc.)
- Via cloud storage (Dropbox, Google Docs, OneDrive etc.)
- Via physical disks and/or email
- Never shared research data
- Other

A2. The last time you shared research data, how interoperable were the data?

- Unstructured documents
- Proprietary file format (e.g. SPSS SAV)
- Standard file format (e.g. CSV, JSON)
- Not applicable/Do not understand

A3. The last time you shared research data, how structured were the data?

- Unstructured documents
- Unclear schema (self-defined columns that were not explicitly documented)
- Standard schema (e.g. SNOMED-coded columns)
- Clear schema (self-defined columns that were documented clearly)
- Not applicable/Do not understand

In the last two years how frequent have you

	Never	Once	Once per year	Once per semester	Once per trimester	Once per month	Twice or more per	Not applicable	Don't know
B4. Deposited data into a DOI-oriented data archive/repository?									
B5. Uploaded your data into "public" web-spaces (not repositories)?									
B6. Provided access to your data by publishing supplement materials for articles?									
B7. Been personally asked to share data?									

Attitude

In your discipline

	Strongly disagree	Moderately disagree	Slightly disagree	Neutral	Slightly agree	Moderately agree	Strongly agree	Not applicable	Don't know
C1. Journals usually require researchers to share data									
C2. Journals can penalize researchers not sharing manuscript related data									

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	Strongly disagree	Moderately disagree	Slightly disagree	Neutral	Slightly agree	Moderately agree	Strongly agree	Not applicable	Don't know
C3. An article is more likely to be accepted for publication if the author provides open access to their data									
C4. It is expected by peers that researchers share data systematically									
C5. Researchers rely on research data shared with them									

Please select the one that best describes your beliefs towards data sharing and reuse

	Strongly Disagree	Moderately disagree	Slightly disagree	Neutral	Slightly agree	Moderately agree	Strongly agree	Not applicable	Don't know
C6. Archiving data and analysis scripts structurally may help me (and direct team members) to reproduce my/our own results in a few years from now									
C7. Sharing research data is my moral obligation because of my funding source									
C8. Sharing research data is my scientific obligation, since it allows verification, replication, and building further research, based on my methods/results									

How important are the following factors when deciding to use other's research data in relation to the data origin?

The data	Very important	Important	Somewhat important	Unimportant	Not at all important	Not applicable	Don't know
C9. Are from someone I know personally							
C10. Are from someone I DON'T know personally but who has a good reputation							

The data	Very important	Important	Somewhat important	Unimportant	Not at all important	Not applicable	Don't know
C11. Are from someone at an institute with a good reputation							
C12. Are from a repository with a good reputation							
C13. Have good documentation and/or metadata							
C14. Are certified or accredited by a third party							
C15. Are commonly used by others							
C16. Have been cited in a publication in the formal literature (journals, books etc.)							

Concerns

What keeps you from sharing your research data with others?

	Strongly disagree	Moderately disagree	Slightly disagree	Neutral	Slightly agree	Moderately agree	Strongly agree	Not applicable	Don't know
D1. GDPR related legal restrictions (e.g. data transfer agreement, controller-processor agreement, consent procedures etc.)									
D2. Non-GDPR related legal restrictions (e.g. copyright, patent law, trademark protection, use protection, etc.)									
D3. Fear of making mistakes when sharing data									
D4. Increased effort of time and/or cost (e.g. organize/annotate, making sure data protection rules are respected, etc.)									
D5. Risk of misinterpretation and/or falsification of data									

	Strongly disagree	Moderately disagree	Slightly disagree	Neutral	Slightly agree	Moderately agree	Strongly agree	Not applicable	Don't know
D6. Potentially undesired commercial use									
D7. Danger of misuse (e.g. military applications, crime)									
D8. Increased competition in the "publish or perish" game									
D9. Not knowing where and how to share data									
D10. Lack of motivation / incentive									

Incentives

What would motivate you to share research data?

	Strongly Disagree	Moderately disagree	Slightly disagree	Neutral	Slightly agree	Moderately agree	Strongly agree	Not applicable	Don't know
E1. Recognition in the scientific community									
E2. Consideration of research data as relevant scientific output in research documentation and evaluations (at project or career level)									
E3. Increased visibility and impact of my own research (e.g. through co-authorships and/or citations in publications resulting from shared research data)									
E4. New contacts and/or opportunities for cooperation with other scientists									
E5. Financial incentives (bonus, expense allowance, discounts in scientific journals)									
E6. Establishment of standards for accountability and appropriate use (Fair Use) of the data									

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	Strongly Disagree	Moderately disagree	Slightly disagree	Neutral	Slightly agree	Moderately agree	Strongly agree	Not applicable	Don't know
E7. Provision of support in the process of making data accessible by your institution									
E8. Increased self-esteem / moral satisfaction									

Appendix 2 - Results

A - Demographics

		N	%
A1. How many years have you been engaged in research activities?	Under 5	15	20.0%
	6-10	16	21.3%
	11-15	20	26.7%
	16-20	5	6.7%
	20+	19	25.3%
	Total	75	100.0%
A2. Concerning research projects, you are mostly responsible for:	Equally responsible for both	46	61.3%
	Execution of research projects	27	36.0%
	Writing of research proposals	2	2.7%
	Total	75	100.0%
A3. Which of the following best describes your primary work sector?	Academic	51	68.0%
	Non-profit	7	9.3%
	Other	8	10.7%
	Private	9	12.0%
	Public	51	68.0%
	Total	75	100.0%
A4. What is your primary funding source for all your projects in the last five years? A country - or subject-specific research funder e.g. a research council	No	45	60.0%
	Yes	30	40.0%
What is your primary funding source for all your projects in the last five years? A corporate/private/commercial organization	No	64	85.3%
	Yes	11	14.7%
What is your primary funding source for all your projects in the last five years? Self-funded	No	66	88.0%
	Yes	9	12.0%
	No	37	49.3%

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What is your primary funding source for all your projects in the last five years? A regional research funder: e.g. European Commission	Yes	38	50.7%
What is your primary funding source for all your projects in the last five years? My institution	No	58	77.3%
	Yes	17	22.7%
What is your primary funding source for all your projects in the last five years? A charity or other 'third sector' funder	No	74	98.7%
	Yes	1	1.3%
What is your primary funding source for all your projects in the last five years? Crowd-funded	No	75	100.0%
	Yes	0	0.0%
What is your primary funding source for all your projects in the last five years? Don't know	No	73	97.3%
	Yes	2	2.7%
What is your primary funding source for all your projects in the last five years? Other	No	75	100.0%
	Yes	0	0.0%
A5. Where do you usually store you research data?	Cloud service	21	26.9%
	Locally	57	73.1%
A6. Have you ever experienced research data loss?	No	62	82.7%
	Yes	13	17.3%
A7. Do you keep back-ups on a location separate from where the data is stored?	No	8	10.7%
	Yes, but only anecdotally	35	46.7%
	Yes, structured daily/weekly/monthly snapshots	32	42.7%
A8. In case you keep backups (online or offline), who can recover the data from your backups?	A General System Administrator of your own organization	20	29.9%
	Only a project-specific peer of yours	17	25.4%
	Only you	27	40.3%
	Support staff of another organization	3	4.5%

B - Data sharing experience

		N	%
B1. The last time you shared research data, how did the recipients gain access?	As supplementary material on publisher website	6	7.7%
	Never shared research data	5	6.4%
	Via cloud storage (Dropbox, Google Docs, OneDrive etc.)	33	42.3%
	Via DOI-oriented data archive/repository (Figshare, Zenodo etc.)	7	9.0%
	Via institutional server/drive (FTP, SMB etc.)	8	10.3%
	Via personal or institutional website	6	7.7%
	Via physical disks and/or email	13	16.7%
	Total	78	100.0%
B2. The last time you shared research data, how interoperable were the data?	Not applicable/Do not understand	9	11.5%
	Proprietary file format (e.g. SPSS SAV)	13	16.7%
	Standard file format (e.g. CSV, JSON)	45	57.7%

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	Unstructured documents	11	14.1%
	Total	78	100.0%
B3. The last time you shared research data, how structured were the data?	Clear schema (self-defined columns that were documented clearly)	37	47.4%
	Not applicable/Do not understand	12	15.4%
	Standard schema (e.g. SNOMED-coded columns)	6	7.7%
	Unclear schema (self-defined columns that were not explicitly documented)	11	14.1%
	Unstructured documents	12	15.4%
	Total	78	100.0%

	Never	Once	Once per year	Once per semester	Once per trimester	Once per month	Twice or more per month	Not applicable	Don't know
In the last two years									
B4. how frequent have you: Deposited data into a DOI-oriented data archive/repository?	52.0%	16.0%	12.0%	5.3%	2.7%	0.0%	1.3%	4.0%	6.7%
B5. how frequent have you: Uploaded your data into "public" web-spaces (not repositories)?	57.3%	16.0%	13.3%	4.0%	2.7%	0.0%	0.0%	4.0%	2.7%
B6. how frequent have you: Provided access to your data by publishing supplement materials for articles?	48.0%	17.3%	17.3%	9.3%	4.0%	0.0%	0.0%	2.7%	1.3%
B7. how frequent have you: Been personally asked to share data?	32.0%	21.3%	17.3%	9.3%	8.0%	4.0%	2.7%	2.7%	2.7%

C - Attitudes

	Strongly disagree	Moderately disagree	Slightly disagree	Neutral	Slightly agree	Moderately agree	Strongly agree	Not applicable	Don't know
In your discipline:									
C1. Journals usually require researchers to share data	8.0%	10.7%	14.7%	14.7%	16.0%	21.3%	12.0%	0.0%	2.7%
C2. Journals can penalize researchers not sharing manuscript related data	13.3%	24.0%	9.3%	12.0%	12.0%	14.7%	1.3%	2.7%	10.7%
C3. An article is more likely to be accepted for publication if the author provides open access to their data	8.0%	16.0%	6.7%	14.7%	8.0%	21.3%	17.3%	0.0%	8.0%
C4. It is expected by peers that researchers share data systematically	4.0%	17.3%	10.7%	24.0%	10.7%	20.0%	12.0%	0.0%	1.3%
C5. Researchers rely on research data shared with them	9.3%	8.0%	8.0%	16.0%	18.7%	17.3%	16.0%	0.0%	6.7%

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	Strongly disagree	Moderately disagree	Slightly disagree	Neutral	Slightly agree	Moderately agree	Strongly agree	Not applicable	Don't know
Please select the one that best describes your beliefs towards data sharing and reuse:									
C6. Archiving data and analysis scripts structurally may help me (and direct team members) to reproduce my/our own results in a few years from now	1.6%	1.6%	3.2%	9.5%	6.3%	28.6%	49.2%	0.0%	0.0%
C7. Sharing research data is my moral obligation because of my funding source	13.3%	6.7%	0.0%	20.0%	12.0%	24.0%	18.7%	4.0%	1.3%
C8. Sharing research data is my scientific obligation, since it allows verification, replication, and building further research, based on my methods/results	4.0%	4.0%	2.7%	9.3%	12.0%	20.0%	42.7%	4.0%	1.3%

	Not at all important	Unimportant	Somewhat important	Important	Very important	Not applicable	Don't know
How important are the following factors when deciding to use other's research data in relation to the data origin?							
C9. Are from someone I know personally	13.3%	21.3%	22.7%	21.3%	16.0%	1.3%	4.0%
C10. Are from someone I DO NOT know personally but who has a good reputation	9.3%	6.7%	32.0%	33.3%	12.0%	2.7%	4.0%
C11. Are from someone at an institute with a good reputation	6.7%	10.7%	30.7%	37.3%	10.7%	1.3%	2.7%
C12. Are from a repository with a good reputation	2.7%	13.3%	22.7%	42.7%	14.7%	1.3%	2.7%
C13. Have good documentation and/or metadata	1.3%	2.7%	9.3%	38.7%	44.0%	0.0%	4.0%
C14. Are certified or accredited by a third party	5.3%	8.0%	33.3%	25.3%	16.0%	2.7%	9.3%
C15. Are commonly used by others	8.0%	18.7%	34.7%	22.7%	9.3%	0.0%	6.7%
C16. Have been cited in a publication in the formal literature (journals, books etc.)	6.7%	9.3%	29.3%	34.7%	17.3%	0.0%	2.7%

D - Concerns

	Strongly disagree	Moderately disagree	Slightly disagree	Neutral	Slightly agree	Moderately agree	Strongly agree	Not applicable	Don't know
What keeps you from sharing your research data with others?:									
D1. GDPR related legal restrictions (e.g. data transfer agreement, controller-processor agreement, consent procedures etc.)	4.0%	1.3%	5.3%	6.7%	24.0%	13.3%	42.7%	2.7%	0.0%

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D2. Non-GDPR related legal restrictions (e.g. copyright, patent law, trademark protection, use protection, etc.)	2.7%	1.3%	5.3%	17.3%	20.0%	17.3%	28.0%	8.0%	0.0%
D3. Fear of making mistakes when sharing data	10.7%	14.7%	9.3%	21.3%	13.3%	22.7%	4.0%	4.0%	0.0%
D4. Increased effort of time and/or cost (e.g. organize/annotate, making sure data protection rules are respected, etc.)	4.0%	9.3%	5.3%	10.7%	22.7%	18.7%	25.3%	2.7%	1.3%
D5. Risk of misinterpretation and/or falsification of data	4.0%	5.3%	9.3%	18.7%	26.7%	20.0%	10.7%	5.3%	0.0%
D6. What keeps you from sharing your research data with others?: Potentially undesired commercial use	1.3%	12.0%	8.0%	20.0%	16.0%	20.0%	16.0%	5.3%	1.3%
D7. Danger of misuse (e.g. military applications, crime)	12.0%	13.3%	8.0%	14.7%	14.7%	14.7%	10.7%	12.0%	0.0%
D8. Increased competition in the "publish or perish" game	9.3%	10.7%	16.0%	16.0%	16.0%	16.0%	12.0%	2.7%	1.3%
D9. Not knowing where and how to share data	16.0%	12.0%	6.7%	17.3%	21.3%	18.7%	5.3%	2.7%	0.0%
D10. Lack of motivation / incentive	12.0%	8.0%	6.7%	17.3%	20.0%	21.3%	12.0%	2.7%	0.0%

E - Incentives

What would motivate you to share research data?:	Strongly disagree	Moderately disagree	Slightly disagree	Neutral	Slightly agree	Moderately agree	Strongly agree	Not applicable	Don't know
E1. Recognition in the scientific community	2.7%	1.3%	0.0%	14.7%	18.7%	33.3%	26.7%	1.3%	1.3%
E2. Consideration of research data as relevant scientific output in research documentation and evaluations (at project or career level)	4.0%	1.3%	0.0%	6.7%	10.7%	40.0%	34.7%	1.3%	1.3%
E3. Increased visibility and impact of my own research (e.g. through co-authorships and/or citations in publications resulting from shared research data)	2.7%	2.7%	0.0%	6.7%	18.7%	33.3%	36.0%	0.0%	0.0%
E4. New contacts and/or opportunities for cooperation with other scientists	2.7%	4.0%	0.0%	4.0%	17.3%	29.3%	41.3%	1.3%	0.0%
E5. Financial incentives (bonus, expense allowance, discounts in scientific journals)	9.3%	2.7%	4.0%	10.7%	20.0%	24.0%	26.7%	1.3%	1.3%

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E6. Establishment of standards for accountability and appropriate use (Fair Use) of the data	4.0%	1.3%	1.3%	16.0%	18.7%	24.0%	30.7%	1.3%	2.7%
E7. Provision of support in the process of making data accessible by your institution	4.0%	0.0%	5.3%	12.0%	10.7%	28.0%	36.0%	1.3%	2.7%
E8. Increased self-esteem / moral satisfaction	9.3%	4.0%	5.3%	29.3%	16.0%	10.7%	20.0%	4.0%	1.3%